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A STUDY TO ASSESS AND EVALUATE THE PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVE DRUGS IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The objectives of the study are to assess and evaluate the prescribing patterns of antihypertensive drugs in patients of a tertiary care teaching hospital, to compare the prescribing patterns of antihypertensive drugs in hypertension and co-morbid conditions with JNC-8 and to determine the distribution of co-morbidities in hypertensive patients. **Methodology:** This prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 6 months. Prescriptions of hypertensive patients admitted in the medicine ward with at least one antihypertensive drug prescribed were collected and were documented in a separate data collection form. The obtained data will be analyzed for average number of antihypertensive drugs per prescription, class of antihypertensive drugs prescribed, distribution of patients according to gender, mode of therapy and distribution of co-morbidities. Appropriateness of the prescription will be analyzed as per JNC-8 guideline. **Result:** In our study it was found that the age group of 60-69 years had the higher incidence of hypertension with male patients more prominent than females. Most of the patient had the BP range of 140-149/90-99mmHg. Co-morbidities were observed in almost all prescriptions, DM was prominent among them. Combination therapy was preferred over monotherapy. Two drug regimens were commonly prescribed among the combination therapy. The prescription showed weak adherence to various recommendations of JNC 8. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that prescribing guidelines should be followed by physicians for better health outcome and improvement in quality of life of patient suffering from hypertension and co-morbidities because these guidelines are based on vigorously conducted various clinical trials.

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INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is one of the major chronic diseases resulting in high morbidity and mortality worldwide. Hypertension is defined as a condition wherein the systolic blood pressure (SBP) is higher than 140 mmHg or a diastolic blood pressure (DBP) higher than 90 mmHg. Hypertension is an established risk factor for cardiovascular disease such as myocardial infarction, arrhythmia, angina pectoris, cardiac failure and for renal complications with shortened expectancy of life. It is therefore important that once diagnosis of hypertension is established, blood pressure should be adequately controlled through regular follow up, life style modification, exercise and effective anti-hypertensive drugs. Hypertension is reported to be the fourth contributor to premature death in developed countries and seventh in developing countries. The increasing prevalence of hypertension is attributed to population growth, ageing and behavioral risk factors, such as unhealthy diet, excess use of alcohol, sedentary lifestyle, obesity and exposure to persistent stress.

Epidemiological studies demonstrated that prevalence of hypertension is increasing rapidly in India, varying from 2% to 25% among urban residence and from 2% to 15% among rural residence in India. It is estimated that the worldwide prevalence of hypertension would increase from 26.4% in 2000 to 29.2% in 2025. The primary objective of antihypertensive therapy is to prevent morbidity and mortality associated with hypertension. The need to improve the global control of high BP has necessitated the stipulation of various hypertension classification and treatment guidelines

The recently published JNC 8 guideline used rigorous evidence-based methods in developing evidence statements and recommendations for BP treatment based on a systematic review of the literature to provide clear recommendations for all clinicians.

A prescription by a doctor may be taken as a reflection of physician's attitude to the disease and the role of the drug in its treatment. It also provides an insight into the nature of health care delivery system. The study of prescribing pattern is a component of medical audit which seeks monitoring, evaluation and necessary modifications in the prescribing practices of the prescribers to achieve rational and cost effective medical care. It is necessary to define prescribing pattern and to identify the irrational prescribing habits to drive a remedial message to the prescribers.

Keeping in view the present study entitled "A study to assess and evaluate the prescribing patterns of anti-hypertensive drugs" is conducted on various facets of anti-hypertensive drugs prescribing at present scenario in SSIMS, a tertiary care hospital, Davangere with objectives of studying prescribing patterns of anti-hypertensive drugs in essential hypertension with some specific co-morbid conditions and compare the same with JNC-8 in the inpatients attending the medicine department.

OBJECTIVE

The objectives of the study are to assess and evaluate the prescribing patterns of antihypertensive drugs in patients of a tertiary care teaching hospital, to compare the prescribing patterns of antihypertensive drugs in hypertension and co-morbid conditions with JNC-8 and to determine the distribution of co-morbidities in hypertensive patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the medicine ward of SSIMS & RC, a tertiary care teaching hospital in Davangere. The study was conducted for a period of 6 months. Achieved sample size was 150 prescriptions. The data about patients were collected from case sheets of inpatients in medicine department of a tertiary care teaching hospital. The study was a prospective observational study. Patient selection was done according to the following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with hypertension above 30 years of age who are prescribed with at least one anti-hypertensive drug.
- Patients with hypertension alone or with other co-morbid conditions like IHD, DM, MI, CKD etc. are included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Seriously ill patients requiring ICU admission.
- Patient admitted to neurology, gynecology and other wards
- Pregnant and lactating women

Ethical Considerations

The ethical clearance for the study was obtained from Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere.

Study Procedure

The study was carried out by regular visits to inpatient medicine departments to collect case sheets from patients according to the inclusion criteria.

The obtained data was analyzed for:

- i. Average number of anti-hypertensive drugs per prescription
- ii. Mode of anti-hypertensive drug therapy
- iii. Distribution of co- morbidities in hypertensive patients.
- iv. Prevalence of hypertension in different age group.
- v. Category wise distribution of anti-hypertensive drugs.
- vi. Appropriateness of the prescription as per JNC-8 guideline

RESULTS

A total of 150 prescriptions were collected, out of which 80(53.33%) were males and 70(46.67%) were females.

Table 1: Gender Wise Distribution of Patients.

GENDER	NO. OF PATIENTS (N=150)	PERCENTAGE
Male	80	53.33%
Female	70	46.67%

Majority of patients were in the age group of 60-69 (36%) followed by 50-59(24%), 70-79 (18.67%), 40-49 (12%), 30-39 (6%), >79 years (3.33%) respectively.

Table 2: Distribution of Age Group.

AGE GROUP	NO. OF PATIENTS (N=150)	PERCENTAGE
30-39	9	6%
40-49	18	12%
50-59	36	24%
60-69	54	36%
70-79	28	18.67%
>79	5	3.33%

Out of 150 hypertensive patients, most number of hypertensive patients were found in the BP range of 140-159/90-99mmHg (47.33%) followed by BP range of \geq 180/110mmHg (26.67%) and the least number of patients were found in the range of 160-179/100-109mmHg (26%).

Table 3: Distribution of Patients According to Blood Pressure Range.

RANGE	NO. OF PATIENTS (N=150)	PERCENTAGE
140-159/90-99mmHg	71	47.33%
160-169/100-109mmHg	39	26%
\geq 180/100mmHg	40	26.67%

Out of 150 prescription collected all prescription contain hypertension associated with other co-morbid condition and the most common co-morbid condition was Diabetes Mellitus(30.67%) followed by CVA(14%), AFI(12.67%), IHD (6.66%), Pneumonia(6%), Seizures(5.33%), CKD(5.33%), Hypothyroidism(2.67%), Angina(2%), Others(14.67%) respectively. Others mainly include COPD, UTI, Jaundice, Meningitis, LRTI, Liver cirrhosis, RA, Osteoporosis.

Table 4: Distribution of Co-morbidities.

NO. OF CO-MORBIDITIES	FREQUENCY (N=150)	PERCENTAGE
Diabetes Mellitus	46	30.67%
CVA	21	14%
AFI	19	12.67%
IHD	10	6.66%
Pneumonia	9	6%
Seizure	8	5.33%
CKD	8	5.33%
Hypothyroidism	4	2.67%
Angina	3	2%
Others	22	14.67%

The preferred antihypertensive drug therapy for patient with hypertension and other co morbid conditions were combination therapy (50.67%) and the remaining patients were prescribed with monotherapy (49.33%). In combination therapy about 15.33% prescriptions contain FDC and 35.34% contain a combination of individual drugs.

Table 5: Mode of Therapy.

MODE OF THERAPY	NO. OF PRESCRIPTIONS	PERCENTAGE
Monotherapy	74	49.33%
Combination therapy	76	50.67%
1) with FDC	23	30.26%
2) without FDC	53	69.74%

Out of the 150 prescriptions 74 prescriptions contain single antihypertensive drug and among them the most commonly prescribed drug was CCB's (51.35%), followed by ARB's (18.92%), FDC (14.86%), β -Blockers (6.76%), Diuretics (6.76%) and ACEI's (1.35%).

Table 6: Monotherapy.

ANTI-HYPERTENSIVE DRUG CLASS	NUMBER OF PRESCRIPTIONS (N=74)	PERCENTAGE
CCB's	38	51.35%
ARB's	14	18.92%
FDC	11	14.86%
β -Blockers	5	6.76%
Diuretics	5	6.76%
ACEI's	1	1.35%

Among 74 prescriptions containing CCB's (51.35%) as monotherapy, three drugs were most commonly prescribed which were Amlodipine (94.74%) followed by Felodipine (2.63%), and Clinidipine (2.63%).

Table 7: Calcium Channel blockers (CCB's).

CCB'S	NO. OF PRESCRIPTION (N=38)	PERCENTAGE
Amlodipine	36	94.74%
Felodipine	1	2.63%
Clinidipine	1	2.63%

- Among Diuretics (6.76%) only drug given was Furosemide, a high ceiling diuretic.
- Ramipril (1.35%) is the only drug which is given as monotherapy among ACEIs.
- Of the total 76 prescription containing combination therapy 33 (43.43%) prescriptions contain two anti hypertensive drugs, three anti hypertensive drugs were prescribed in 16 (21.05%) prescriptions and four drugs were prescribed in 3 (3.94%) prescriptions. About 24 (31.58%) contains combinations of antihypertensive drugs along with FDC.

Table 11: Combination Therapy.

DRUG REGIMEN	NO. OF PATIENTS (N=33)	PERCENTAGE
Two Drug Regimen	33	43.43%
Three Drug Regimen	16	21.05%
Four Drug Regimen	3	3.94%
With FDC	24	31.58%

Among the 33 prescriptions containing two drug regimen 16 prescriptions contain a combination of ARB's+CCB's (48.49%) followed by Diuretics+CCB's (18.18%), Diuretics +ARB's (15.15%), CCB's+CCB's (12.12%), ACEI's+ β -Blockers (6.06%).

Table 12: Two drug regimen.

DRUG REGIMEN	NO: OF PRESCRIPTIONS	PERCENTAGE
ARB's+CCB's	16	48.49%
Diuretics+CCB's	6	18.18%
Diuretics+ARB's	5	15.15%
CCB's+CCB's	4	12.12%
ACEI's+ β -BLOCKERs	2	6.06%

Three drug regimen was found to be 21.05% of the combination therapy and among them 37.5% was Diuretics+ARB's+CCB's followed by ARB's+CCB's+ β -Blockers and Diuretics+CCB's+ β -Blockers with 12.5%, Centrally acting drugs+CCB's+Diuretics, Diuretic+Diuretic+CCB's, Diuretic+CCB's+(α + β) Blocker, Diuretic+CCB's+CCB's, Diuretic+ARB's+ Centrally acting drugs, Diuretic+ARB's+(α + β) Blocker each with 6.25%.

Table 13: Three drug regimen.

DRUG REGIMEN	NO: OF PRESCRIPTION (n=16)	PERCENTAGE
Diuretics+ARB's+CCBs	6	37.5%
ARB's+CCBs+ β -Blockers	2	12.5%
Diuretics+CCB's+ β -Blockers	2	12.5%
Centrally acting drugs+CCBs+Diuretics	1	6.25%
Diuretics+Diuretics+CCBs	1	6.25%
Diuretics+CCBs+(α + β) Blocker	1	6.25%
Diuretics+CCBs+CCBs	1	6.25%
Diuretics+ARB's+Centrally acting drug	1	6.25%
Diuretics+ARB's+(α + β) Blockers	1	6.25%

Four drug regimens were rarely prescribed in combination therapy (3.94%). Among them most commonly prescribed combination was Diuretics+ARB's+CCBs+ β -Blockers (66.67%) followed by the combination of Diuretics+CCBs+CCBs+ α -Blockers (33.33%).

Table 14: Four drug regimen.

DRUG REGIMEN	NO. OF PRESCRIPTION	PERCENTAGE
Diuretics+ ARB's+CCBs+ β -Blockers	2	66.67%
Diuretics+CCBs+CCBs+ α -Blockers	1	33.33%

DISCUSSION

- Hypertension is one of the major chronic diseases resulting in high morbidity and mortality worldwide. We undertook the study of prescription patterns of anti-hypertensive drugs in order to assess and evaluate the prescribing attitude of the physicians and drug utilization in the patients admitted to the medicine department of a tertiary care teaching hospital.
- A total of 150 patients were enrolled in this study. Out of 150 prescriptions analyzed 80 patients (53.33%) were males and 70 patients (46.67%) were females. This study is found to be similar with the various other studies. Nithin Kothari et al. and Sheron Joseph et al. also had the same finding.
- This present study revealed that the patients belonged to the age group of 60-69 years were more prominent with hypertension (36%) followed by 50-59 (24%) which is in compliance with the study done by Annamalai Maduram et al.
- In our study out of 150 patients 71 patients (47.33%) were categorised under the blood pressure range of 140-159/90-99mmHg. V Pavani et al. conducted a comparable study which revealed that out of 360 patients 204 were belonged to 140-159/90-99mmHg.
- This present study revealed that all prescriptions evaluated were suffering with co-morbid conditions which are in contrast to the studies done by Amruth et al which found that patients suffering with co-morbid conditions were 88%. Among the various co-morbidities cardiovascular diseases plays an important threat.
- In our study, combination therapy was commonly prescribed. Almost 76 prescriptions (50.67%) were prescribed with combination therapy which include both with FDC and without FDC followed by monotherapy. Etuk et al reported that only 20% of cases were prescribed with monotherapy.⁷ This finding is in contrast to the result of Kuchake et al. wherein 61.48% patients were treated with a single anti-hypertensive drug and 38.52% patients were treated with anti-hypertensive drug combinations.
- Out of 74 patients who underwent monotherapy for the treatment of hypertension (51.35%) were prescribed with CCBs followed by ARB (18.92%). Among CCBs the most commonly prescribed drug was Amlodipine. The study conducted by Kuchake et al. revealed that CCBs are the drug of choice for hypertensive patients as monotherapy followed by B-Blocker which was less in this study.
- In two drugs regimen ARB+CCB (48.49%) was common followed by ARB+Diuretics (18.18%). This findings was similar to the study conducted by Anand et al. where multiple drug therapy was more common than single drug therapy and two drug combinations were mostly prescribed (67.7%) followed by three drug combination (27.5%) and four drug combination (4.9%).
- In this present study the patient receiving three drug regimen was Diuretics+ARB+CCB (37.5%) followed by ARB+CCB+B-Blocker (12.5%) which was not similar to the study conducted by V Pavani et al. which reported that maximum number of patients were treated with Diuretics+ARB+B-blockers(21.2%) followed by ARB+ACEI+Diuretics (19.1%).
- In our study Diuretics+ARB+CCB+B-blocker 66.67% followed by Diuretics+CCB+CCB+A-Blocker 33.33% were the four drug combination prescribed. This study is comparable to the study conducted by V. Pavani.
- According to the study conducted by Amruth et al. the frequently prescribed fixed dose combination of drugs were ARB+Diuretics 54% (Telmisartan + Hydrochlorothiazide) and CCB+ARB 2% (Amlodipine+Telmisartan) was prescribed least number of times. Whereas the present study reveals that ARB+CCB 36.37% are frequently prescribed FDC followed by ARB+Diuretics 27.39%.
- Average number of drugs prescribed per prescription was found to be 1.82 which was similar to the findings of the study done by Kothari et.al. This study revealed that prescriptions showed weak adherence to JNC-8

CONCLUSION

STRENGTH OF THE STUDY

- i. It may provide physicians with the feedback on their prescribing pattern of anti-hypertensive drugs when compared to the standard criteria.
- ii. The results of the study may provide insight to the utilization of anti-hypertensive drugs in a number of hypertensive patients within the given time period.
- iii. Appropriateness of the prescriptions analyzed will encourage and direct prescribers in making modifications in prescribing pattern and avoiding potentially inappropriate drugs.
- iv. The results obtained in the study can be further used for assessing the rational prescription of the antihypertensive drugs.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Data were collected from only one institution; therefore the population is relatively homogenous

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